

MEDICAL SCIENCES

LONG-TERM RESULT OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PATHOLOGY OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

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Abstract

For an objective assessment of the symptoms of TMJ disease, differential diagnosis, as well as for dynamic monitoring of the effectiveness of treatment, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive functional examination, including electromyographic and kinesiographic studies. Computerized electromyography provides an objective assessment of the bioelectrical activity of the masticatory muscles in case of occlusal disorders, changes in the height of the lower part of the face and their relationship with the development of pain syndrome in the maxillo-facial region, and also allows monitoring the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment at all stages.

Keywords: temporomandibular joint, electromyography, occlusal disorders, occlusal splints.

Computerized kinesiography allows us to suspect the presence of occlusal disorders during protrusive and laterotrusive movements of the lower jaw. [1.2.3] With normally functioning TMJ, protrusion and retrusion are identical curves, the trajectories of which must coincide. In pathology, these trajectories may diverge. Also, a kinesiographic study is necessary to assess adaptation to the formed **position of the lower jaw (end of the splint therapy stage)** [4.5].

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment using an occlusal splint for 3 months in patients with TMJ pathology.

Material and methods.

We conducted a clinical and functional examination of 32 patients. Patients of the CCS Clinic of the Moscow State Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, were examined with complaints of pain in the masticatory muscles, difficulty chewing food, and clicking in the TMJ area. The patients were examined using a functional diagnostic complex, including electrovibrography, computerized electromyography, computerized kinesiography, and transcutaneous electrical neurostimulation. Joint sounds were recorded using 2 piezoelectric sensors located in headphones, which were placed on the patient's skin in the projection of the TMJ. To make a diagnosis, a special table and digital values obtained using an electrovibrograph were used. After a preliminary diagnosis based on the results of electrovibrography, patients underwent MRI diagnostics of TMJ in order to confirm or refute the diagnosis. The diagnosis obtained using the electrovibrography method was confirmed by MRI of the TMJ in all cases. Electrovisography is an inexpensive preliminary diagnostic method and determines the need for an expensive MRI study. Electromyography and kinesiography were performed in patients with

musculo-articular dysfunction of the TMJ (disc disorders) before treatment and at the stages of splint therapy at 2 weeks, 1 and 3 months. Results. The values of the obtained electromyography indicators before treatment in 32 patients with TMJ pathology during the "relative physiological rest of the lower jaw" test ranged from 2.16 to 3.95 mV, which characterizes the hyperactive state of the muscles, while during treatment using an occlusal splint within 3 months, in 81.3% of patients, bioelectric potentials approached the physiological norm and ranged from 0.8 to 1.9 mV (N=0.6-1.5 mV). The results of indicators of symmetry and synergy of the masticatory and temporal muscles in 32 patients with muscular-articular dysfunction before treatment during the "maximum volitional compression of the dentition" test ranged from 37 to 79% (N = 80-100%). When comparing the obtained data with the indicators before treatment and 3 months after the start of treatment using an occlusal splint, in 90.6% of patients, the bioelectric potentials were close to the physiological norm and amounted to more than 80%. We obtained data from computerized kinesiography of patients with TMJ pathology after treatment using an occlusal splint for 3 months, as a result of which positive dynamics in treatment were identified, the trajectories of the lower jaw were aligned, and in all 32 patients canine guidance was adjusted on the right and left. In all of the 19 patients who had deviation or deviation, the deviation of the lower jaw was eliminated during treatment.

Conclusion.

The use of computerized kinesiography and electromyography methods makes it possible to instrumentally monitor the functional state of the dental system before treatment, carry out dynamic monitoring and document results at all stages of treatment. This proves the need to use the kinesiographic and electromyo-

graphic method in patients with muscular-articular dysfunction for objective monitoring of the results of orthopedic treatment at all stages of preliminary treatment: occlusal splint, temporary fixed orthopedic structures and permanent orthopedic treatment, monitoring in the long term. The ability to document studies at all stages of treatment allows you to build a doctor's defense in the event of conflict situations. After completing the splint therapy stage, the patients' bioelectrical indicators of the functional activity of the masticatory muscles (electromyography and kinesiography) approached the physiological norm.

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